

2022 IEEE Signal Processing Cup: Synthetic Speech Attribution

Team SIPL Report

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Abstract—This report describes Team SIPL’s solution to the 2022 Signal Processing Cup challenge. We developed a method that, given an audio recording of a synthetically generated speech track, can detect which method among a list of candidates has been used to synthesize the speech, and can also accommodate for unknown speech synthesis algorithms. Our solution relies on speech signal analysis using signal processing and machine learning techniques, particularly deep neural networks. Using an ensemble of features and classifiers allows our method to achieve high performance and to be robust to noise. Another strategy we use for noise robustness is data augmentation for training with noisy audio tracks. Applying our solution to Part 1 of the challenge (noise free samples) yielded an accuracy of 92.2%, and applying it to Part 2 of the challenge (noisy samples) yielded an accuracy of 78.4%.

Index Terms—Anti-spoofing, deepfake, forensics, audio, Signal Processing Cup 2022

I. INTRODUCTION

The Signal Processing Cup (SP Cup) [1] is an annual competition that encourages student teams to solve real-world problems using signal processing methods. The competition’s final is held at the ICASSP conference. The challenge this year focuses on forensic issues related to the malicious use of synthetic speech. The goal is to develop a method for detecting voice deepfakes produced by speech synthesizers. Given an audio recording, it should be able to determine which method, from a list of candidates, has been used to synthesize the speech. The developed method should be robust to noise and capable of operating in an open-set scenario where audio tracks produced by new speech synthesizers unseen in training appear in testing, requiring the classifier not only to accurately classify known synthesizers but also to effectively identify unknown synthesizers.

In recent years much effort has been devoted to the development of forensic detectors capable of distinguishing between original and synthetically generated speech recordings. One notable effort in this direction is ASVspoo [2] - a series of community led biannual challenges that promotes the development of countermeasures to protect automatic speaker verification from the threat of spoofing. However, in this and other research efforts, the problem of attributing a synthetic

speech track to the generator used to synthesize it has received less attention. Another algorithmic challenge that has received less attention and that it is important to address is the robustness of such detectors to noise.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

A high-level block diagram of the proposed solution is depicted in Fig. 1. This solution is a hybrid ensemble based on handcrafted and deep features fed into a set of classifiers, classic and based on deep neural networks. Using an ensemble of features and classifiers allows our method to achieve high performance and to be robust to noise. The outputs of these classifiers are compared and counted in order to determine whether the audio track was generated by one of the five known synthesizers (and which one) or by an unknown synthesizer. Since the classifiers were only trained on tracks synthesized by known synthesizers, high agreement between classifiers with high confidence scores indicates a known synthesizer, whereas low agreement between classifiers or low confidence scores indicates an unknown synthesizer.

A. Feature Extraction

Based on previous literature [2]–[4] and our own experience, we identified a set of features that are informative for the problem at hand. We extract the following features:

- Mel-frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC) [5] – Represent the spectral envelope of the signal on a nonlinear perceptual mel scale. MFCC are commonly used as features in speech recognition and other audio processing applications.
- Linear Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (LFCC) [5] – Unlike the MFCC, represent cepstral coefficients on a linear frequency scale. LFCC better capture spectral characteristics in the high frequency region and are more robust to speech reverberations.
- Constant Q Cepstral Coefficients (CQCC) [6] – Specifically designed for speech spoofing countermeasures. The benefit of CQCC features stems from a variable spectro-temporal resolution, which captures reliably signs of manipulation indicative of spoofing attacks.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed solution.

- Gammatone Filterbank Cepstral Coefficients (GTCC) [7] - Replace the triangular filterbank in the MFCC with a series of Gammatone filters that emphasize different frequency bands. Compared to MFCC, GTCC are reported to be more robust to additive noise.
- Modified Group Delay (MGD) [4] – GD is defined as the frequency differential of the phase spectrum, and is smoothed to obtain the MGD. It enhances important properties of the short-time speech spectrum envelope and complements signal magnitude-based features.
- wav2vec 2.0 [8] - a speech encoder model consisting of a convolution neural network (CNN) and a transformer. The former extracts a sequence of feature vectors from 20 ms windows of the input waveform and the latter transforms it to a representation that captures the information from the entire sequence. This model has recently become popular for speech processing due to the ability of a pre-trained wav2vec 2.0 network to extract highly informative features for various speech tasks such as speech recognition or emotion recognition.

Note that we have also investigated the Short-term and Long-term (STLT) [9] - a recently introduced feature for speech spoofing countermeasures that models speech as an autoregressive process with multiple different orders. However, we decided not to include this feature in our solution due to its high computational complexity.

Each audio track is divided into short overlapping windows (20 to 35 msec), and the acoustic features for each window are extracted, yielding a feature vector for each coefficient. We also augment each window, except for the wav2vec features, with first- and second-order differentials (i.e., Δ and Δ^2 components).

B. Classification

The ensemble uses two types of classifiers. The first classifier is a collection of support vector machine (SVM) binary learners [10]. In order to capture the coefficient statistics while being independent of the length of the audio track, we compute four robust statistics for each feature vector – mean, median, 5th percentile, and 95th percentile. These four statistics of all coefficients of all features form a feature matrix that is used to classify the audio track.

The second classifier is based on deep neural networks. Its architecture is inspired by [11], [12] and combines a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network. The rationale behind this combination is that CNNs and LSTMs have complementary modeling capabilities, as CNNs are good at mapping features to a more separable space and LSTMs are good at temporal modeling. The CNN has the following layers: conv2D, leaky ReLU, average pooling, batch normalization, dropout, conv2D, leaky ReLU, batch normalization, dropout, fully connected, fully connected, softmax. The second sub-network is a bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) that consists of two LSTMs, one taking the input in a forward direction, and the other in a backwards direction. BiLSTMs increase the amount of information available to the network by improving the context available to the algorithm. In contrast to the SVM classifier, we exploit the temporal modeling capability of LSTMs and feed to the deep network the raw handcrafted features (rather than their statistics). Extracting the deep wav2vec 2.0 features is more intricate since a pre-trained wav2vec 2.0 model fine-tuned for speech recognition should be adapted to the task of speech synthesizer recognition. This adaptation is performed by transfer learning according to [13]. In short, the outputs of several layers from the pre-trained model are combined

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix for the simplified problem in which the audio tracks are generated only by known synthesizers and are not contaminated by noise. The results are for an SVM classifier using statistics of the MFCC, LFCC and CQCC coefficients. The data consists of 5,000 samples from known synthesizers from Part 1 of the competition (4,500 were used for training and 500 for testing).

with trainable weights which are learned jointly with the downstream model.

III. TRAINING AND RESULTS

We first investigate a simplified problem in which the audio tracks are generated only by known synthesizers and are not contaminated by noise. In this configuration, we train an SVM classifier using statistics of the MFCC, LFCC and CQCC coefficients (top branch in Fig. 1). As shown in the confusion matrix of the results in Fig. 2, even with these simple features and one classic classifier, the results are excellent, with more than 99% overall accuracy. We conclude that this configuration is relatively easy to solve and that the two main challenges to tackle in order to achieve good results in this competition are to design an algorithm (1) capable of recognizing unknown synthesizers (2) that is noise robust.

A. Unknown Detection

We have implemented and investigated several methods for novelty detection (also known as anomaly detection or open-set problem) in order to recognize unknown synthesizers such as the Mahalanobis distance, one-class SVM and the DOC algorithm [14], with no improvement in results. Therefore we decided to recognize unknown synthesizers based on the agreement of different classifiers in the ensemble as well as the confidence score produced by these classifiers. The decision rules differ between Parts 1 and 2 since different features and different classifiers behave differently for noise free samples versus noisy samples.

B. Noise Robustness

Noise robustness is improved through three means – selection of robust features, data augmentation, and pre-processing. We have checked the performance of SVM classification with different features and with the addition of white gaussian noise

Fig. 3. Robustness of different features to White Gaussian Noise. The results are for an SVM classifier using feature coefficient statistics. MGD demonstrates high noise robustness.

Fig. 4. Robustness of different features to reverberations. The strength of reverberations increases on the x-axis from left to right. The results are for an SVM classifier using feature coefficient statistics. MGD demonstrates high robustness to reverberations.

Fig. 5. Robustness of different features to MP3 compression. The results are for an SVM classifier using feature coefficient statistics. GTCC and MGD demonstrate high robustness to reverberations.

(WGN) (Fig. 3), reverberations (Fig. 4), and MP3 compression (Fig. 5). In all three figures, clean speech is on the left, and the amount of noise increases on the x-axis from left to right. As

expected, performance for clean speech is the greatest and it deteriorates as the amount of noise increases. For clean speech, MFCC and GTCC show the greatest performance. MGD demonstrates high robustness in all three cases. GTCC demonstrates high robustness to MP3 compression. Based on these results, we design our final decision rules for Parts 1 and 2.

In Part 2, we want our classifiers to learn how to operate effectively in noisy conditions, so we perform data augmentation that adds noise to the clean samples, and train the classifiers with these noisy samples. We augment the speech randomly with WGN in the [20 0] dB range, reverberations with the parameters pre-delay and decay factor in the [0 1] range (affect the size of the room being modeled), and MP3 compression in the [15 3] Kbps range. In total, we used 13,500 audio tracks for training in Part 2. Additional noise robustness is achieved by performing speech enhancement as a pre-processing stage. Although speech enhancement mitigates noise, it may distort the signal. We therefore train the classifiers with samples after enhancement. Namely, we perform speech enhancement for both training samples (after data augmentation with noise) and test samples. The enhancement is performed using the Optimally-Modified Log-Spectral Amplitude (OM-LSA) speech estimator [15], [16].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The method described in this report can recognize which speech synthesizer from a list of candidates was used to synthesize a speech track, and can also recognize unknown speech synthesis algorithms. For this purpose, we used an ensemble of different features and classifiers, both classical and based on deep neural networks. We demonstrated that the challenge is relatively easy to solve when the synthesizers are known in advance and there is no noise. Furthermore, we have developed a number of strategies to deal with the more difficult challenge when this is not the case. The final method, applying these strategies, yielded an accuracy of 92.2% in Part 1 of the challenge and an accuracy of 78.4% in Part 2 of the challenge. Our code is supplied as a supplementary to this report.

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REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE Signal Processing Society. Signal Processing Cup 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://signalprocessingsociety.org/community-involvement/signal-processing-cup>
- [2] M. Todisco, X. Wang, V. Vestman, M. Sahidullah, H. Delgado, A. Nautsch, J. Yamagishi, N. Evans, T. Kinnunen, and K. A. Lee, "ASVspoof 2019: Future horizons in spoofed and fake audio detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.05441*, 2019.
- [3] A. Nautsch, X. Wang, N. Evans, T. H. Kinnunen, V. Vestman, M. Todisco, H. Delgado, M. Sahidullah, J. Yamagishi, and K. A. Lee, "ASVspoof 2019: Spoofing countermeasures for the detection of synthesized, converted and replayed speech," *IEEE Transactions on Biometrics, Behavior, and Identity Science*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 252–265, 2021.
- [4] X. Wang and J. Yamagishi, "A practical guide to logical access voice presentation attack detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.03321*, 2022.
- [5] S. Davis and P. Mermelstein, "Comparison of parametric representations for monosyllabic word recognition in continuously spoken sentences," *IEEE transactions on acoustics, speech, and signal processing*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 357–366, 1980.
- [6] M. Todisco, H. Delgado, and N. W. Evans, "A new feature for automatic speaker verification anti-spoofing: Constant q cepstral coefficients," in *Odyssey*, vol. 2016, 2016, pp. 283–290.
- [7] Y. Shao, Z. Jin, D. Wang, and S. Srinivasan, "An auditory-based feature for robust speech recognition," in *2009 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 4625–4628.
- [8] A. Baeovski, Y. Zhou, A. Mohamed, and M. Auli, "wav2vec 2.0: A framework for self-supervised learning of speech representations," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 33, pp. 12 449–12 460, 2020.
- [9] C. Borrelli, P. Bestagini, F. Antonacci, A. Sarti, and S. Tubaro, "Synthetic speech detection through short-term and long-term prediction traces," *EURASIP Journal on Information Security*, vol. 2021, no. 1, pp. 1–14, 2021.
- [10] E. L. Allwein, R. E. Schapire, and Y. Singer, "Reducing multiclass to binary: A unifying approach for margin classifiers," *Journal of machine learning research*, vol. 1, no. Dec, pp. 113–141, 2000.
- [11] T. N. Sainath, O. Vinyals, A. Senior, and H. Sak, "Convolutional, long short-term memory, fully connected deep neural networks," in *2015 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 4580–4584.
- [12] J. Zhao, X. Mao, and L. Chen, "Speech emotion recognition using deep 1d & 2d cnn lstm networks," *Biomedical signal processing and control*, vol. 47, pp. 312–323, 2019.
- [13] L. Pepino, P. Riera, and L. Ferrer, "Emotion recognition from speech using wav2vec 2.0 embeddings," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.03502*, 2021.
- [14] L. Shu, H. Xu, and B. Liu, "DOC: Deep open classification of text documents," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1709.08716*, 2017.
- [15] I. Cohen and B. Berdugo, "Speech enhancement for non-stationary noise environments," *Signal processing*, vol. 81, no. 11, pp. 2403–2418, 2001.
- [16] I. Cohen, "Noise spectrum estimation in adverse environments: Improved minima controlled recursive averaging," *IEEE Transactions on speech and audio processing*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 466–475, 2003.